

DEVELOPMENT AND ASSESSMENT OF AN INSTRUCTIONAL PACKAGE IN TEACHING FUNDAMENTALS OF CLASSICAL BALLET

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Development and Assessment of an Instructional Package in Teaching Fundamentals of Classical Ballet

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Abstract

This study developed an Instructional Package for Teaching the Fundamentals of Classical Ballet. This study followed the Research and Development (R&D) Design in developing the instructional package for teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet. The quasi-experimental research design was also used to determine the effectiveness of the development of the instructional package in teaching the fundamentals of ballet. The study was conducted in Tupi National High School during the Third Quarter of School Year 2018-2019. The instructional package was evaluated in terms of its content, instructional quality, and technical quality. After it was evaluated, the instructional package was implemented to determine its effectiveness. Five and two information technology experts evaluated the instructional video using the evaluation tool. Two classes were utilized and designated as the control group and the experimental group to determine the effectiveness of the instructional package. The evaluation results of the instructional package revealed its excellent content, instructional, and technical quality. The study's findings also revealed that the instructional package is an effective tool for teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet. The results indicated that the instructional package is a more effective tool. It is recommended that teachers use the instructional package to teach the fundamentals of classical ballet because it enhances students' learning performance.

Keywords: *special program in the arts, instructional package, classical ballet*

Introduction

The advent of technology has affected many aspects of the teaching and learning process. Different strategies and methods were developed using technology to facilitate teaching and maximize students' learning. On the other hand, the manners in which students learn are also influenced by technology. Computers are now extensively used by teachers to facilitate classroom instruction.

Teachers' teaching methods affect students' academic achievement and relationships with others. Suitable teaching methods help to establish better rapport between teachers and students (McCusker, 2013). Many studies have shown the advantages of using technology in classroom instruction. Technology can be used to establish meaningful projects to engage students in critical thinking and problem-solving. Technology can be used to restructure and redesign the classroom to produce an environment that promotes the development of higher-order thinking skills (Kurt, 2010). Keser, Huseyin, and Ozdamli (2011) stressed that technology increases student collaboration, which is a highly effective tool for learning. Students cooperatively work together to create projects or learn from one another by reading the work of their peers.

Physical Education is one of the skills development subjects offered in the Junior High Schools. Technology has the potential to facilitate more effective instruction in physical education. According to Eberline and Richards (2013), many physical education teachers have traditionally relied on observations as a primary assessment method in determining student activity levels. However, recent advances in physical activity technology provide more valid and reliable measurements that can help document student performance. Armed with data gathered through technology, physical education teachers become better equipped to convince various stakeholders of the merits of a quality physical education program. Cawley, Frisvoldc, and Meyerhoeferd (2013) emphasized that teaching physical education can be challenging for many reasons, from a lack of equipment to keeping students engaged. To meet these challenges, some educators turn to technology to create more dynamic classes that work for students with a wide range of fitness levels.

In the Philippines, implementing the Basic Education Curriculum (K to 12) gave rise to offering the Special Curricular Programs in the Junior and Senior High Schools. As part of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, revisions have been made to the curriculum of Special Programs (DepEd Order No. 46, series of 2012). At Tupi National High School, the Special Program on the Arts, a major in Dance, is offered at the Junior High School. One of the topics taught in the Special Program on the Arts major in Dance among the Grade 10 students is classical ballet. This study focused on developing an instructional package for teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet. In the instructional package, the video was used as a learning material to facilitate the teaching of classical ballet.

Classical ballet was chosen as the subject of this study because it was observed that there is a lack of instructional materials, especially technology-assisted instruction, in teaching classical ballet lessons. Further, there needs to be more ballet teachers who teach in the Special Program on the Arts with a major in Dance. Because of this, teachers teaching classical ballet cannot adequately demonstrate the different fundamental positions and exercises in ballet.

Based on the preceding considerations of technology's benefits and potential to facilitate effective instruction in physical education, this study was conducted to develop an instructional package for teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet. The study was conducted in Tupi National High School, specifically among students in the Special Program on the Arts (SPA) majoring in Dance.

Research Questions

This study developed and assessed the effectiveness of an Instructional Package in Teaching the Fundamentals of Classical Ballet. Specifically, this study did the following:

1. What instructional package for teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet can be developed?
2. How is the Instructional Package in Teaching the Fundamentals of Classical Ballet evaluated in terms of:
 - 2.1. content;
 - 2.2. instructional quality; and
 - 2.3. technical quality?
3. How Effective is the Instructional Package in Teaching the Fundamentals of Classical Ballet?

Research Design

This study followed the Research and Development (R&D) Design in developing the instructional package for teaching the fundamentals of ballet. The R&D Model is a process by which knowledge and information are gathered, and the data and information collected will be analyzed and serve as the basis for the design and development of the study output (Wang et al., 2013). This study gathers and analyses data and information to serve as the basis for developing an instructional video.

The quasi-experimental research design, which used a two-group and non-random experimental design, was also used to determine the effectiveness of the instructional package in teaching the fundamentals of ballet. There were two groups of students or classes: the control and experimental groups. The students in the control group were taught using the conventional method of classical ballet, and the students in the experimental group were taught using the instructional package.

Respondents

The data in this study were gathered from different sources and respondents.

The Five experts and two information technology experts evaluated the instructional video using the evaluation tool.

Two classes were utilized and designated as the control group and the experimental group to determine the effectiveness of the instructional package. The study's respondents who composed the two classes are the 18 Grade 10 students in the Special Program on the Arts major in Dance. Nine students were in the control group, and nine were in the experimental group. In determining the students who comprised the control and experimental groups, basic exercises were given to the 18 Grade 10 students in the Special Program on the Arts major in Dance. The students were divided into two groups based on the results of the warm-up exercise. After the students were divided into two groups, drawing of lots was used to determine which would be designated as the control and experimental groups.

One (1) MAPEH teacher, two (2) dance teachers, and one (1) ballet expert evaluated the learning performances of the students in the control group and the experimental group.

Instruments

The instruments used the Evaluation Tools on the instructional video's content, instructional quality, and technical quality. The evaluation tool was adapted from the instrument Alegre (2012) used in a study on developing a computer-aided instructional tool in linear equations.

To determine the effectiveness of the instructional package, the material was implemented for the Grade 10 students designated as the experimental group. After the instructional package was used, the student's actual performance was evaluated through a rubric. The rubric was also used to evaluate the performance of the Grade 10 students in the control group, which used the conventional teaching method. The results of the evaluation of the performance of the students in both the control and the experimental groups were then compared.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the developed instructional package for teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet, including the results of evaluating the instructional package in terms of content, instructional quality, technical quality, and effectiveness of the instructional package.

Instructional Package in Teaching the Fundamentals of Classical Ballet

This study developed an instructional package for teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet. The package was based on the Curriculum Guide for Special Program in the Arts in Major Dance.

Topics

Based on the curriculum guide, the topics on Classical Ballet that were included in the instructional package are (1) the Evolution of

Classical Ballet, (2) the Positions of the Head, which are erect, inclined, turned, raised, and lowered; (3) Positions of the Arms includes Bras bas, First Position, Second Position, Third Position, Fourth Position, and Fifth Position; (4) Positions of the Feet includes First Position, Second Position, Third Position, Fourth Position, and Fifth Position; (5) Combinations of the Head, Arms and Feet; (6) Barre Exercises includes Plie and Grand Plie, Tendu, Degage, Developpe, Rond de Jambe, Frappe and Grand battement; and (7) Center Exercises includes Adagio, Battement Tendu, Grand Battement, Balance, Pirouette, Saute, Changement, Glissade, Assemble, Jete, Chaines and Pique Turns.

Learning Competencies

The learning competencies of the instructional package were also based on the curriculum guide in Classical Ballet for Special Program in the Arts major in Dance. These competencies are the following: The learner: (1) outlines the evolution of ballet history; (2) identifies advanced ballet techniques and skills, famous ballet pieces, and their choreographers; (3) executes the fundamental positions of the head, the arms, and the feet in ballet; and (4) executes varied barre and center work exercises in ballet.

Instructional Activities

The instructional activities of the instructional package include the procedures in the delivery of instruction and the learning material used in the delivery of instruction. The delivery of instruction is facilitated by the lesson plan, which was formulated for each of the topics on the fundamental positions and exercises in classical ballet. The instructional video is the learning material used in teaching the fundamental positions and exercises of classical ballet. The technical quality of the instructional was evaluated by the Information Technology (IT) experts. The instructional video was used by the teacher to teach the fundamentals of classical ballet.

Result of the Evaluation of the Contents of the Instructional Package

The study's evaluation of the instructional package revealed that the evaluators gave excellent ratings on all the indicators of content validity, with a factor average of 4.56. The preceding result means that the instructional package's contents are generally adequate, accurate, and well-defined. The contents are also appropriate to the intended learners' ability level and emphasize performance-based learning. The contents of the instructional package were based on the curriculum guide prescribed by the Department of Education (DepEd) for teaching classical ballet among the students in the Special Program in the Arts (SPA) major in Dance. The topics are well-organized, engaging, relevant to the learning objectives, and aligned with the curriculum's sequence of objectives and skills.

Table 1. *Result of the Evaluation of the Contents of the Instructional Package*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The contents are adequate.	4.50	Excellent
2. The contents are accurate/well defined.	4.50	Excellent
3. The topics are well organized.	4.67	Excellent
4. The topics are relevant to the learning objectives.	4.50	Excellent
5. The topics are interesting.	4.50	Excellent
6. The contents are free of bias and stereotypes.	4.50	Excellent
7. The contents are appropriate to the ability level of the intended learners of the course.	4.67	Excellent
8. The topics are aligned with the sequenced of objectives and skills in the curriculum.	4.50	Excellent
9. It emphasizes performance-based learning.	4.67	Excellent
Factor Average	4.56	Excellent

The result of the Evaluation of the Instructional Quality of the Instructional Package

The results in Table 2 revealed that the evaluators gave excellent ratings on all the indicators describing the instructional quality of the instructional package, with a factor average of 4.50.

Table 2. *The result of the Evaluation of the Instructional Quality of the Instructional Package*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. It is a good supplement to the curriculum.	4.50	Excellent
2. It addresses the concerns of the students learning the fundamental positions and exercises in classical ballet.	4.67	Excellent
3. The instructional material facilitates collaborative learning.	4.50	Excellent
4. It facilitates the achievement of instructional objectives.	4.33	Excellent
5. It integrates student's previous experiences in classical ballet.	4.50	Excellent
6. It reflects current trend in P.E. instruction.	4.50	Excellent
7. It allows independent learning and creativity.	4.50	Excellent
8. It supports different modalities and intelligences.	4.33	Excellent
9. The instructions are clearly stated.	4.50	Excellent
10. It gives appropriate motivation.	4.67	Excellent
Factor Average	4.50	Excellent

The instructional package is a good supplement to the curriculum, especially since there is a lack of teaching materials for classical ballet. It also addresses the students' concerns about learning classical ballet's fundamental positions and exercises. The instructional package also facilitates collaborative learning among the students, enables the achievement of instructional objectives, provides clear instructions, allows for independent learning and creativity, and supports the different modalities and intelligences.

The results in Table 2 revealed that the evaluators gave excellent ratings on all the indicators describing the instructional quality of the instructional package, with a factor average of 4.50.

Result of the Evaluation of the Technical Quality of the Instructional Package

Table 3 shows the study's results in evaluating the instructional package in terms of technical quality. The evaluators gave excellent ratings in all the indicators describing the technical quality of the video in the instructional package to facilitate the delivery of the lessons in classical ballet, with a factor average of 4.70. This result means that the video is of excellent quality regarding technical aspects.

The video, which was developed as the learning material to be used in the delivery of the lessons in classical ballet, precisely the fundamental positions and exercises, is technically valid. As evaluated, the instructional video is easy to navigate, its manipulative controls are comprehensive and directive, and it allows the learners to control the pace of learning. The layout and design of the instructional video are appropriate, and the intended users can easily and independently use the instructional package. Further, the video developed for the instructional package is aesthetically pleasing. Its resolution and the sound or voice in the video are also clear.

Table 3. *Result of the Evaluation of the Technical Quality of the Instructional Package*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The instructional video is easy to navigate.	5.00	Excellent
2. The instructional video allows the learners to control the pace of learning.	5.00	Excellent
3. The graphics is excellent.	4.50	Excellent
4. The layout and design are appropriate.	4.50	Excellent
5. The manipulative controls are comprehensive and directive.	4.50	Excellent
6. The video runs quickly with minimum wait time.	4.50	Excellent
7. Intended users can easily and independently use the instructional video.	5.00	Excellent
8. The instructional video is aesthetically pleasing.	4.50	Excellent
9. The resolution of the video is clear.	5.00	Excellent
10. The sound/voice in the video is clear.	4.50	Excellent
Factor Average	4.70	Excellent

Effectiveness of the Instructional Package

This section presents and interprets the result of the test of the difference between the performance of the control and experimental groups. The result of the statistical analysis is shown in Table 4.

The result in Table 4 shows that the mean performance of the students in the control group after the classical ballet lessons were delivered through the conventional teaching method is 3.67. Based on the rubrics used to evaluate the students' performance, this mean can be interpreted as very good. The student's performance in a specific position or exercise is correct primarily but seemed confused; the transition was satisfactory, but the student could have shown more control.

Table 4. *Result of the Test of Difference Between the Performance of the Control Group and the Experimental Group*

Group	Mean	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Control	3.67	3.06	0.003	With significant difference
Experimental	4.21			

The mean result of the student's performance in the experimental group after the lessons in classical ballet were delivered using the instructional package is 4.21. This result can be verbally interpreted as excellent. The student perfectly executed the position or exercise with no hesitation. The position of the exercise is precise, and the student shows complete self-confidence during transitions.

The test result for the difference between the student's performances in the control and experimental groups has a t-value of 3.06 and a p-value of 0.003. This means a significant difference exists between the student's performance in the control and experimental groups at a 0.05 significance level.

The result shown in Table 4 revealed that the experimental group students performed better than those in the control group. This implies that using an instructional package facilitated by a video teaching classical ballet is effective compared to the conventional teaching method. Using video technology helps students learn better and retain their acquired knowledge. The instructional video can help the students learn because they can use it repeatedly and master a particular position or exercise, even without the teacher's guidance. On the other hand, in the conventional teaching method, the student can only perform with the guidance of the teacher, who will

demonstrate a particular position or exercise.

The result of the evaluation of the content of the instructional package in teaching fundamentals of classical ballet is excellent. This means that the content is adequate and relevant to the learning objectives. According to Sawangsri (2016), the learning package should be complete and relate to the course content, which creates the learning effectively. In addition, the instructional package is of higher quality and effectively enhances student learning and motivation compared to a conventional teaching method (Sirathanakul, 2015). This indicates that the content of the instructional package is effective in teaching classical ballet.

The result of the evaluation of the instructional quality of the instructional package is excellent. This implies that the instructional package supports the learners' modalities and intelligences. The result supports Bull's study (2013). This multimedia material can help learners with high spatial ability draw from their verbal and visual repositories when presented with contiguous word and picture presentations. Moreover, higher instructional quality can improve student satisfaction (Cornillez et al., 2019). Hence, the student's satisfaction with the instructional package is high (Tangthong & Aktimagool, 2016).

The technical quality of the instructional package was evaluated, and the results were excellent. This implies that the instructional video allows the learners to control the pace of learning. The results support the study of Olabo et al. (2021), which states that using instructional videos in secondary school students is effective for learning. In addition, using an ICT-based instructional package can significantly motivate learners and stimulate learning (Adelana et al., 2021).

The student's performance in the control group after using the conventional method of teaching classical ballet was excellent. On the other hand, the results of the student's performance in the experimental group were excellent. This means that using an instructional package was practical rather than the conventional way of teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet. The results support the study of Yaki & Babagana (2016), which states that the technological instructional package can significantly improve students' performance. In addition, unlike lecture methods, using computer-assisted instructional packages can improve the student's performance (Chado & OKwori, 2015). Moreover, interactive instructional packages can improve students in terms of academic achievement, skill transfer, and retention compared to conventional instruction alone (Ajimotokan et al., 2015).

Moreover, according to Ngamprapasom (2014), the learning package is one of the innovations vital to enhancing learners' learning achievement. This is because the learning package is a combination of multimedia. It is helpful for teachers to transfer their knowledge and experience into concrete formats. Teachers have opportunities to participate in learning activities concerned with individual differences. Learners can practice learning individually or as a group. After using the learning package, the learning achievement is higher. Wood (2005) also stated that using digital video was a worthwhile aid to the education process from the participants' perspective in the project. It was regarded as a valuable aid to learning and maintaining student engagement.

Conclusions

The instructional package for teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet was based on the curriculum guide of a special arts program. The topics on Classical Ballet that were included in the instructional package are (1) the Evolution of Classical Ballet, (2) the Positions of the Head, which are erect, inclined, turned, raised, and lowered; (3) Positions of the Arms includes Bras bas, First Position, Second Position, Third Position, Fourth Position, and Fifth Position; (4) Positions of the Feet includes First Position, Second Position, Third Position, Fourth Position, and Fifth Position; (5) Combinations of the Head, Arms, and Feet; (6) Barre Exercises includes Plie and Grand Plie, Tendu, Degage, Developpe, Rond de Jambe, Frappe, and Grand battement; and (7) Center Exercises includes Adagio, Battement Tendu, Grand Battement, Balance, Pirouette, Saute, Changement, Glissade, Assemble, Jete, Chaines, and Pique Turns.

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The instructional activities of the instructional package include the procedures in the delivery of instruction and the learning material used in the delivery of instruction. The delivery of instruction is facilitated by the lesson plan, which was formulated for each of the topics on the fundamental positions and exercises in classical ballet. The instructional video is the learning material used in teaching the fundamental positions and exercises of classical ballet. The teacher used the instructional video to teach the fundamentals of classical ballet.

Based on the study's findings, the instructional package is excellent in terms of its contents, instructional quality, and technical quality. The contents and topics included in the instructional package are adequate and accurate based on the curriculum's requirements. Because of its instructional quality, the instructional package is also a good supplement for the delivery of instruction in classical ballet.

The instructional package is also effective in teaching the fundamentals of classical ballet. The study's results indicate that the students in the experimental group who used the instructional package were better than those in the control group who used the conventional method of teaching.

Teachers can use the instructional package to teach the fundamentals of classical ballet because it is effective in enhancing students'

learning performance. In addition, teachers must be trained to properly utilize the instructional package in teaching the fundamental positions and exercises of classical ballet. Moreover, a study may be conducted by other researchers to validate the result of this study on the effectiveness of the instructional package.

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